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Quantum Computing as a Pathway to Develop Drugs for Undruggable proteins

Issue/Problem

A wide range of human proteins are considered 'undruggable' because of their relatively flat functional interfaces, lacking the pockets that would typically be targets for drug treatments. The difficulty in devising innovative treatments for these proteins is compounded by the long and costly drug development process. Quantum computing offers a potential pathway to both speed up drug development and explore treatments that target 'undruggable' proteins.

Description of the Problem

Quantum computing's potential has yet to be broadly harnessed, because current machines remain constrained by errors known as '[noise](#).' These errors can be caused by electromagnetic radiation, temperature fluctuations, and a range of other environmental factors that can be difficult to isolate and control for. This noise represents a major developmental hurdle for quantum computing's practical application.

Results

On January 22, 2025 [a study](#) co-led by University of Toronto researchers and Insilico Medicine [announced](#) that it had demonstrated the potential of combining quantum computing with generative AI and classical computing methods to develop targeted molecules for undruggable proteins as part of the drug development pipeline.

The study combined quantum computers with classical computing networks to design small molecules targeting KRAS mutations, using a custom dataset of over one million molecules developed in part by AI, to screen potential inhibitors. This hybrid approach identified 15 potential inhibitors, with two being marked as viable candidates for further development.

Lessons Learned

The methodology provides hope that quantum computing and generative AI can together eventually reduce the required time for preclinical discovery phases. The project underlines the importance of consortiums that bring together academia, industry and government in pursuing innovation in the quantum computing and drug discovery fields, with the [Acceleration Consortium](#) providing the framework for the project.

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